

COMBINING ABILITY STUDIES FOR QUANTITATIVE CHARACTERS IN LINSEED (*Linum usitatissimum* L.)A.R. Jadhav^{1*}, P.B. Wadikar², V.A. Kulkarni³ and D.D.⁴ Lathe^{1,3,4} Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding COA, Latur, Maharashtra, India.² Associate professor, Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding COA, Latur. Maharashtra, India.

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MS Received: 18.05.2024; MS Revised: 15.06.2024; MS Accepted: 16.06.2024

MS 3215

(RESEARCH PAPER IN GENETICS AND PLANT BREEDING,,)

Abstract:

Twenty-one crosses generated by using four lines and three testers was carried out to study the combining ability for seed yield and related traits in linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) and evaluated against standard checks LSL-93 and TL-99 in randomized block design for ten quantitative characters. Analysis for combining ability revealed that, significant differences among the mean squares for line x testers for all characters for seed yield per plant (g). Among the lines, Meera and Binwa and the tester GS-36 displayed high GCA effect and considered good general combiners for most of the characters for seed yield per plant (g). Significant positive SCA effect for seed yield per plant was displayed by Neelam x PKVNL-260, EC-1628 x GS-36 and Meera x PKVNL-260. These crosses have been exhibited highest SCA effect over seed yield per plant (g). Hybrids involving good combiner can be used through pedigree breeding for the improvement of any characters while the crosses showed highly significant positive SCA effect can be exploited for heterosis breeding programme.

Keywords: Combining ability, GCA effect, SCA effect, linseed, line x tester

Introduction

Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) is an oldest domesticated and economically important industrial non-edible oilseed crop which is being cultivated for seed and its fiber since centuries (Damania, 1997) the whole plant has commercial use directly or indirectly and has capability to substantiate the existing natural demand for oil. The seed consist of an oil that 33 to 47 per cent its considered most widely botanical source of Omega-3 fatty acid, constitute up to 65 % of total fatty acid composition. It also used an ingredient for varnish, paintings, saving materials from getting wet. Most of the investigator are of opinion that the wild flax linum plant genus *agustifolium* found in Mediterranean location may be the relative of the cultivated species genus *Linum usitatissimum* as the species have equal frame range (2n=30). It is grown for consumption and rich source of fiber in area colder climates where the average temperature is below 15 degree. The success of any hybridization programme depends on combining ability of parents used in crossing programme (Hallaur and Miranda, 1981). Combining ability provide reliable information on the nature magnitude of gene effects that contribute to expression of quantitative trait and help plant breeders to select appropriate parents for hybridization (Kempthorne, 1957). In view of the above facts and in view of above facts and in order to develop and identify productive varieties, the present investigation were undertaken Line x Tester analysis to derive information on the genetic parameters for various quantitative characters.

Material and Methods

The experimental material consists of ten diverse genotypes *viz.*, Binwa, Meera, Neelam, FR-11, EC-1444, EC-1628, Mutant-04, GS-36, GIF-White and PKVNL-260 were crossed in all possible combinations using line x tester mating design to obtain 21 hybrids of linseed, during *Rabi*, 2022-23. This experiment was carried out at experimental farm Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, College of Agriculture Latur, VNMKV Parbhani, (Maharashtra) India. These 21 hybrids of four lines and three testers with two standard checks evaluated in randomized block design with two replications, in single row plot of 2 m length with spacing of 30 cm row to row and 5 cm plant to plant, within a row in *Rabi*, 2023-24. All recommended agronomic practices were adopted to raise healthy crop. The data were recorded in five randomly selected competitive plant from each plot for plant height (cm), number of branches per plant, number of capsule per plant, number of seeds per capsule, 1000 seed weight, seed yield per plant (g) and harvest index (%) were subjected to statistical analysis. The character days to 50 per cent flowering and days to maturity were recorded on whole plot basis. The oil content (%) in seed was analysed using NMR. The mean value of the recorded data was subjected to analysis of variance using the statistical analysis. The data recorded on F₁s were analysed as per method suggested by Kempthorne (1957).

Results and Discussion

The analysed data showed effect for all the characters under study. The analysis of variance for present investigation in presented (Table.1). The mean square for treatments, parents and crosses is highly significant for all characters under study except harvest index (%) indicated that there is presence of variability in experimental material under investigation, Based on combining ability effects, the parents were categorized in three groups as good, average and poor combiners, positive GCA effects were considered as good general combiners whereas parents with negative GCA effects were designated as poor general combiners. SCA of is effect of non-additive gene action of characters is indicator for the selection of hybrid combination. Therefore, a highly significant SCA effect is desirable for a successful hybrid breeding programme.

The analysis for combining ability revealed that, mean squares due to GCA were higher in magnitude than SCA for most of the characters indicating GCA is the predominant cause of variation in these characters. However, variance due to SCA was higher in magnitude than the respective GCA variance for the characters *viz.*, number of branches per plant, number of capsules per plant, number of seed per capsule, 1000 seed weight and seed yield per plant. signifies preponderance of non-additive gene action can be improved by bi-parental mating or reciprocal recurrent selection. Among lines, Meera was the good general combiner for the characters *viz.*, days to 50 % flowering (-1.54**), number of branches per plant (0.343*), number of capsule per plant (18.49*) and seed yield per plant (g) (0.833**). Line Binwa was a good general combiner for characters *viz.*, days to 50 % flowering (-1.964**), days to maturity (-0.740**), number of branches per plant (0.936**), number of seeds per capsule (0.117*) and seed yield per plant (g) (0.567**). Among testers, GS-36 had significant GCA effect for characters *viz.*, plant height (cm) (4.76**), number of branches per plant (0.289**), number of seed per capsule (0.564**), and seed yield per plant (g) (0.333**). A close relation between GCA and *per se* performance of the parents was observed for most of the characters under study (Table 2) Salini *et al.* (2016), Rathva *et al.* (2023) and Jadala *et al.* (2023).

The cross Neelam x PKVNL-260 (1.07**), EC-1628 x GS-36 (1.067**), and Meera x PKVNL-260 (0.545*) showed positively significant SCA effect for seed yield per plant (g). Neelam x PKVNL-260 reported positively significant SCA effect for number of capsule per plant (12.476**) and 1000 seed weight (g) (1.101**), EC-1628 x GS-36 recorded significantly positive SCA effect for character number of seed per capsule (0.852**), while Meera x PKVNL-260 exhibited positively significant SCA effect for number of braches per plant (0.944**) and number of capsule per plant (10.760**) (Table 3). When the SCA effects of the crosses were compared to their mean performance, it became clear that the ranking based on SCA effects did not always match the ranking based on performance *per se*, and crosses with high mean performance did not always have high SCA effects. Same results were also reported by Pali and Mehta (2014),

Mishra *et al.* (2013), Kumar *et al.* (2016), Naik, B.S. (2017), Nirala *et al.* (2018) and Velamuri *et al.* (2021).

Conclusion

Hybrids involving good combiner can be used through pedigree breeding for the improvement of any characters. The *per se* performance of the crosses and their SCA effects did not consistently correlate. It is possible that estimating SCA effects may not always result in the best hybrid combination option. Therefore, it may be more practical and realistic to select the best possible cross combination based on *per se* performance.

References

1. **Anil Sirsath¹ , D. K. Zate² And L.N. Jawale, 2021**, Combining Ability Studies In Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentas* L. Moench), VOL. XII, ISSUE XXXX, Oct 2021 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, Page 90-96.
2. **Arkhe V.A¹ , D.K.Patil¹ , V.K.Gite², Abubakkar.Syed 2020**, Combining Ability Studies For Yield And Yield Components In Pigeonpea [*Cajanus Cajan* (L.) Millsp] , VOL. X, ISSUE XXXIII, APRIL 2020 Multilogic In Science ISSN 2277-7601, Page 506-510.
3. **Damania, A.B. 1997**. Near-eastern crop diversity and its global migration In: The origin of Agriculture and crop domestication, processing of Harlan symposium (ICARDA 1997).
4. **Halluar, A.R. & Miranda, J.B. 1981**. Quantitative genetics in Maize Breeding, Iowa state university press, Ames, Iowa, USA.
5. **Kempthorne, O. 1957**. An introduction to genetic statistics. London. 2nd edition John. Wiley and Sons. Iconic Newyork, Chapman, and Hall limited PP, 468-470.
6. **Kumar, N., Paul, S., Chaudhary, H. K., Sood, V. K., Mishra, S. K., Singh, A. D., & Devi, R. (2016)**. Combining ability, gene action & heterosis for seed yield & its attributes in Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.). *Sabra Journal of Breeding & Genetics*, 48(4).
7. **Manish Sharma¹ and Y.G.Shadakshari 2021**, Combining Ability And Nature Of Gene Effects Controlling Seed Yield And Its Component Traits In Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.), VOL. X, ISSUE XXXVI, APRIL 2021 MULTILOGIC IN SCIENCE ISSN 2277-7601, Page 1717-1720.
8. **Mishra, R., Marker, S., Bhatnagar, V. & Mahto, D. (2013)**. Combining ability and heterosis for seed yield and its components in Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.). *Advances in Life Sciences*. 2(1), 44-47.

9. **Naik, B.S. 2017**. Combining ability analysis conditions in the north-central plateau zone of Odisha in India. *International Journal of Current Research*. 9(6), 52445-52447.
10. **Nirala. R.B. P., Rani, N., Acharya. S.S., Vishwakarma, R., Ranjan, T., Prasad, B.D & Pal, A.K. 2018**. Combining ability analysis for grain yield & its component traits in Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.). *Current Journal of Applied Science and Technology*. 31(4), 1-12.
11. **Pali, V & Mahto, N. 2014**. Combining ability and heterosis for seed yield and its quantitative traits in Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.). *The Bioscan*. 4(2), 701-706.
12. **Pravendra Kumar¹ , P. K. Singh² , G. C. Yadav³ , C. N. Ram³ , Satish Yadav¹ and S.K Verma, 2019**, Studies On Combining Ability In Tomato (*Solanum Ly Copersicum* (Mill.) Wettst.), Vol. Viii, Special Issue, National Seminar On Rttepsr Nduat Ayodhya-2019 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601
13. **Sanket R. Rathi¹*, Satish S. Nichal², Swapnil M. Janjal³ and Shailesh M. Gawande 2019**, Detection Of Promising Hybrids On The Basis Of Standard Heterosis And Combining Ability In Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.), VOL. IX, ISSUE XXIX, APRIL 2019 Multilogic In Science ISSN 2277-7601, Page 235-240.
14. **Velamuri, A.S., Sreemoy, B & Sriraj R. 2021**. A review on the effect of combining ability on yield & yield attributing characteristics in flax seed/Linseed (*Linum Usitatissimum* L.) *International Journal of Agricultural Science & Research*. 11(1), 2321-0087.
15. **Jadala, R., Nair, M.B., Jadhav, R., Manapure, P. R. & Jagzape, A. B 2023**. Combining Ability Analysis in Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) *Biological Forum-An International Journal* 15 (10), 1124-1128.
16. **Rathva, P., Patel, M., Solanki, U. & Pali, V. 2023**. Combining ability analysis seed yield and its attributing traits in Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) *International Journal of plant and Soil science*, 5(3), 251-284.
17. **Shalini, S., Sohan, R., Ekhlague, A. & Shanti, B. 2016**. Combining ability analysis for yield and quality traits in Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.). *Advances in Life Sciences*. 5(4), 1297-1304.
18. **S.M. Shinde¹*, V.L. Gawande² , B.B. Ghaley³ And V.T. Kogde, 2024**, Combining Ability Estimates From Line X Tester Mating Design In Upland Cotton, VOL. XIV, ISSUE XXXXX, Feb. To April. 2024 Multilogic In Science ISSN 2277-7601, Page 73-78.

Table 1 Analysis of variance for combining ability for ten different characters including parents in linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.)

Source of Variation	d.f.	Days to 50 per cent flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	Number of branches per plant	Number of capsules per plant	Number of seeds per capsule	1000 seed weight (g)	Seed yield per plant (g)	Harvest index (%)	Oil content (%)
Replications	1	1.36	1.27	8.38	0.26	39.40	0.24	0.27	0.00	0.014	0.45
Treatments	30	28.92**	35.01**	76.35**	2.08**	609.31**	0.74**	1.57**	1.01**	23.09	17.28**
Parents	9	40.86**	20.78**	82.53**	0.81**	292.47**	0.54**	1.81**	1.48**	27.55	25.33**
Lines	6	11.64**	7.62**	56.55**	0.99**	364.77**	0.61**	2.54**	0.51**	21.25	27.69**
Testers	2	148.16**	67.13**	176.64**	0.17	21.41	0.54**	0.50*	0.16	5.14	18.39**
Lines v/s Testers	1	1.60	7.09	50.19**	1.01*	4.82**	0.14	0.11	1.01**	110.18**	25.03**
Parents v/s Crosses	1	19.04**	1.47	151.09**	15.27**	2890.89**	0.88**	3.91**	3.47**	1.15	0.64
Crosses	20	24.04**	43.09**	69.79**	1.99**	637.81**	0.82**	1.35**	1.13**	22.18	14.49**
Error	30	2.42	1.81	3.13	0.15	23.38	0.09	0.12	0.07	12.62	0.42

* and ** indicated significance at 5 and 1 per cent level, respectively

Table 2 Estimates of general combining ability (GCA) of lines and testers for yield and contributing traits linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.)

Treatment	Days to 50 per cent flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height(cm)	No. of branches per plant	No. of capsule per plant	No. of seed per Capsule	1000 Seed Weight (cm)	Seed yield per plant (g)	Harvest index (%)	Oil content %
Line										
Binwa	-1.964**	-0.74**	-6.310**	0.936**	13.03	0.117*	-0.170**	0.567**	0.944	-1.090**
Meera	-1.54**	0.593	2.020	0.343**	18.49*	-0.033**	-0.391**	0.833**	0.219	-1.155**
Neelam	0.086	-1.700**	4.170*	0.243**	12.97	-0.083**	0.512**	-0.050**	3.086	1.236**
FR-11	0.669	0.540	-0.276**	0.168*	-1.44**	-0.250**	0.595**	-0.117**	-0.092**	2.413**
EC-1444	-1.340**	0.160	-1.490**	-3.55**	-7.58**	0.330**	-0.248**	-0.200**	-0.191**	-0.857**
EC-1628	1.330	1.126	-1.240**	-1.07**	-19.25**	-0.167**	-0.375**	0.417**	0.368	1.245**
Mutant-04	2.760*	-0.540**	3.120*	0.25**	-16.22**	-0.417	0.077	-0.617**	-4.334**	-2.492**
S.E.(Gi)	0.63	0.55	0.72	0.16	1.97	0.126	0.144	0.112	1.45	0.26
S.E.(Gi-Gj)	0.89	0.77	1.02	0.22	2.79	0.17	0.20	0.15	2.05	0.37
CD @5%	1.87	1.62	2.13	0.47	5.82	0.37	0.42	0.33	4.27	0.78
CD @1%	2.55	2.21	2.91	0.65	7.94	0.50	0.58	0.45	5.83	1.07
Testers										
GS-36	2.40**	3.038**	4.76**	0.289**	5.49	0.564**	-0.346	0.333**	-0.420**	-1.626**
GIF-White	1.007*	2.217**	0.43	0.023	1.35	-0.300**	0.097**	-0.118**	-1.479**	-0.225**
PKVNL-260	-3.40**	-5.25**	-5.20**	-312**	-6.84**	-0.264**	0.249**	-0.145**	1.899	1.881**
S.E.(Gi)	0.41	0.36	0.47	0.10	1.29	0.082	0.09	0.07	0.94	0.17
S.E.(Gi-Gj)	0.58	0.50	0.66	0.14	1.82	0.11	0.13	0.10	1.34	0.24
CD @5%	1.22	1.60	1.39	0.31	3.81	0.24	0.27	0.21	2.80	0.51
CD @1%	1.67	1.45	1.90	0.42	5.20	0.33	0.37	0.29	3.82	0.70

* and ** indicated significance at 5 and 1 per cent level, respectively

Table. 3 Estimation of specific combining ability (SCA) for ten characters in linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.)

Sr no.	Treatment	Days to 50 per cent flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	No. of branches per plant	No. of capsule per plant	No. of seed per Capsule	1000 Seed Weight (g)	Seed yield per plant (g)	Harvest index (%)	Oil content %
1	Binwa × GS-36	0.95	-3.905**	1.831	-0.945**	-13.710**	-0.481	0.428	-0.517*	-1.235	-0.222
2	Binwa × GIF-White	-0.057	1.617	-1.933	0.390	13.380**	0.433	-1.060**	0.355	2.509	-2.348**
3	Binwa × PKVNL260	-0.893	2.288*	0.102	0.555	0.330	0.048	0.633*	0.162	-1.274	2.570**
4	Meera × GS-36	-1.417	2.329*	-3.002	-0.402	-5.325	0.119	0.589*	-0.033	-1.480	0.398
5	Meera × GIF-White	-1.524	-2.550*	3.133*	-0.541	-5.435	-0.417	0.206	-0.512*	0.349	-0.583
6	Meera × PKVNL260	2.940*	0.221	-0.131	0.944**	10.760**	0.298	-0.796**	0.545*	1.131	0.185
7	Neelam × GS-36	-1.00	-0.071	-1.552	-0.757*	-11.859**	-0.031	-1.054**	-0.700*	2.648	-0.499
8	Neelam × GIF-White	1.093	-2.750**	1.483	0.759*	-0.618	-0.417	-0.047	-0.379	-1.643	3.030**
9	Neelam × PKVNL260	-0.093	2.821**	0.069	-0.001	12.476**	0.448	1.101**	1.079**	-1.005	-2.531**
10	FR-11 × GS-36	0.067	-1.371	3.898**	0.468	12.770**	-0.364	0.313	-0.083	2.652	-1.390**
11	FR-11 × GIF-White	2.460*	2.700*	-1.667	0.939**	6.025	-0.050	-0.580*	0.238	1.660	0.553
12	FR-11 × PKVNL260	-2.526*	-1.329*	-2.231	-1.406**	-18.795**	0.114	0.268	-0.155	-4.312	0.837
13	EC-1444 × GS-36	1.33	2.762**	-1.936	0.291	6.208	0.252	-0.989**	0.100	0.390	1.190*
14	EC-1444 × GIF-White	-3.624**	-4.417**	-3.350*	0.312	-10.051**	-0.133	1.113**	0.271	0.874	0.673
15	EC-1444 × PKVNL260	2.29	1.655	5.286**	-0.603*	3.84	-0.119	-0.124	-0.371	-1.264	-1.863**
16	EC-1628 × GS-36	1.35	0.292	0.264	0.400	2.575	0.852**	0.133	1.067**	-1.293	0.893
17	EC-1628 × GIF-White	0.44	3.117**	3.400*	-0.320	1.815	-0.283	0.580*	-0.262	-2.835	-1.078*
18	EC-1628 × PKVNL260	-1.793	-3.412**	-3.664**	-0.080	-4.390	-0.569*	-0.712**	-0.805**	4.128	0.185
19	Mutant-04 × GS-36	-1.283	-0.038	0.498	0.946**	9.341	-0.348	0.581*	0.167	-1.682	-0.370
20	Mutant-04 × GIF-White	1.210	2.283*	-1.067	-1.538**	-5.118	0.867**	-0.212	0.288	-0.913	-0.247
21	Mutant-04 × PKVNL260	0.074	-2.245**	0.569	0.592*	-4.224	-0.519*	-0.369	-0.455*	2.595	0.617
	SE±	1.70	0.95	1.25	0.27	3.41	0.21	0.24	0.19	2.51	0.46

*and** indicated significance at 1 and 5 per cent level respectively